

Impact of Repeated Reading Strategy in the Development of Reading Fluency of the Struggling Readers in Grade 7

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Abstract:- Reading fluency is a crucial skill for academic and personal success, as it involves the ability to read accurately, quickly, and with expression. Fluent readers can recognize words automatically, allocate mental resources to understand the text, and make connections between words and ideas. One effective instructional approach for enhancing reading fluency among learners is the Repeated Reading Strategy. This study aimed to examine the effects of this strategy on Grade 7 struggling readers at Pres. Jose P. Laurel National High School. Thirty students participated in the study, which employed experimental research with a pre-test and post-test one-group design. The study focused on three aspects of reading fluency: accuracy, rate, and prosody. The Repeated Reading Strategy was implemented through modelling fluent reading, making error correction, and tracking reading progress.

The initial performance level of the struggling readers was low in terms of accuracy, rate, and prosody. However, after using the Repeated Reading Strategy, there was a significant improvement in all three variables. The increase in accuracy, rate, and prosody scores had a large effect size, indicating a significant impact on the students' performance. In conclusion, the Repeated Reading Strategy effectively improved the reading fluency of Grade 7 struggling readers. This study suggests that incorporating this strategy into classroom instruction can be an effective approach to enhance the reading fluency of students facing difficulties in fluent reading.

Keywords:- Reading fluency, repeated reading strategy, struggling readers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading is recognized as a crucial skill for academic success and personal development. It serves as a foundation for learning across various disciplines, equipping students with essential competencies. However, the Philippines is facing a learning crisis, especially in reading. According to the World Bank, the majority of Filipino children at a late primary age lack proficiency in reading. This situation has been further exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has disrupted the educational system for two years.

Even prior to the pandemic, reading problems were prevalent among Filipino learners. The 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) results revealed that Filipino students scored lower in reading compared to their counterparts in other countries. Additionally, the Philippines had the highest percentage of low achievers in reading among all participating nations in the PISA. This deficiency in basic reading and comprehension skills has had a detrimental impact on students' performance in English, Mathematics, and Science.

Recognizing the need to address this challenge, the Department of Education has introduced the Learning Recovery Continuity Plan (LRCP) Framework to bridge the learning gaps caused by the pandemic. The framework emphasizes the importance of remediation and intervention, with a particular focus on improving reading abilities. The DepEd aims to intensify reading programs and interventions to facilitate students' catch-up and accelerate their learning progress.

Aligned with the LRCP Program, this research focuses on implementing the Repeated Reading Strategy to enhance reading fluency among secondary-level learners. Fluency is considered a vital component of reading comprehension, and by developing fluency, students can improve their accuracy, rate, and prosody in reading. The researcher believes that the Repeated Reading Strategy will help learners overcome difficulties in word recognition, as it has been supported by previous studies that suggest fluency development leads to improved reading comprehension.

Wolf [1] defines Reading fluency as the automatic and effortless reading of printed text, where the reader can connect words to form meaningful expressions at a faster pace. Wolf [1] argues that reading fluency is characterized by an individual's ability to read a text with appropriate speed, accuracy, and expression. Wolf & Katzir-Cohen [2] states that at this stage, decoding becomes automatic and effortless, resulting in smooth, accurate reading with appropriate prosody, while the reader's attention is focused on comprehension. Reading fluency is considered an essential skill and a prerequisite for reading comprehension, as emphasized by Tinda et al. [3] and Rasinski [4]. They contend that fluency plays a crucial role in comprehension, which is

the ultimate purpose of reading. In essence, Tavakoli [5] argues that reading fluency signifies the accuracy and speed with which learners expressively read a given text.

One approach to developing fluency among learners is through the implementation of Repeated Readings. Cox [6] asserts that this strategy aims to assist students who have limited experience in reading fluently by building their confidence, speed, and ability to process words automatically. Padeliaadu and Botsas[7] describe this method as an evidence-based approach to fluency instruction when implemented effectively. They highlight key elements of a successful Repeated Reading Lesson, including modeling of fluent reading, positive feedback and correction from adults, and goal-setting, reinforcement, and self-monitoring. The authors also note that some methods of reading fluency instruction incorporate the use of a timer, where students are encouraged to read as many words as possible within a specific time frame (typically one or two minutes). Conversely, the reading teacher may time how long it takes for a student to read a list of words or a passage. However, it is important to emphasize to students that speed alone is not the sole focus of their reading; they should also strive for accuracy and adhere to punctuation rules and other conventions.

In her article on Understanding Assessing Fluency, Harsbrouck[8] explores the three key components of fluency: accuracy, rate, and prosody. She explains that researchers have devised a simple and brief procedure to measure students' oral reading speed and accuracy using regular classroom texts. This procedure involves assessing students individually as they read aloud from an unfamiliar passage of text for one minute, with the goal of determining the number of words they can read correctly within that time. This assessment yields a words-correct-per-minute (WCPM) score. Regarding prosody, which encompasses elements such as expression, volume, phrasing, and smoothness, it serves as a critical indicator of a student's fluency. Educators often utilize a four-level scale initially developed for the 1992 National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) in reading to evaluate the quality of a student's reading prosody. Researchers can employ this scoring guide to measure the prosody level and progress of struggling readers identified in their study.

With all the above-mentioned concepts regarding repeated reading strategy, the researcher is confident that they will contribute significantly to the development of the reading fluency of an individual since repeated practice is considered to bring success as far as honing skills is concerned. Moreover, the researcher believes that determining if the learners' fluency is appropriate for their grade is important in developing their reading skills and in providing necessary intervention and fluency instructions that will support and help them in leveling up their current fluency level with accuracy, appropriate rate and prosody.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of conducting this study is to examine the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy as a reading intervention in developing reading fluency among struggling readers in Grade 7. The specific objectives of the study are twofold.

Firstly, the study aims to determine if the utilization of the Repeated Reading Strategy improves the reading fluency of Grade 7 struggling readers. By implementing this strategy and measuring its impact on the participants' reading abilities, the study seeks to establish whether repeated reading exercises contribute to increased reading fluency and improved overall reading skills.

Secondly, the study aims to evaluate the impact of the Repeated Reading Strategy on the reading habits of Grade 7 struggling readers. It intends to assess whether the implementation of this strategy encourages students to develop better reading habits, such as regular practice and self-monitoring of progress. By examining changes in reading habits, the study seeks to understand the broader effects of the Repeated Reading Strategy on students' approach to reading and their motivation to improve their skills.

By achieving these objectives, the study aims to contribute to the understanding of effective reading interventions and provide insights for educators, parents, and policymakers in supporting struggling readers.

III. METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a pre-experimental method of research, specifically a One-Group Pretest- Posttest Research design. According to Reichardt[9], this design involves measuring the same dependent variable in a single group of participants before (pretest) and after (posttest) administering a treatment. In this study, a non-random group of 30 struggling readers in Grade 7, which were determined based on their pretest scores in the Phil-IRI Oral Reading Assessment, were exposed to an intervention/treatment utilizing the Repeated Reading Strategy. The impact of the intervention on the development of reading fluency among the identified learners was assessed through the comparison of their pre- and post-test scores.

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy in improving the reading fluency of struggling readers in Grade 7. By utilizing the One-Group Pretest-Posttest design, the researcher was able to determine the impact of the intervention on the participants' reading fluency development. The findings of this study had provided valuable insights to educators and practitioners regarding the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy as a teaching tool for struggling readers in Grade 7.

The study involved a group of 30 struggling readers who were enrolled at Pres. Jose P. Laurel National High School for the School Year 2022-2023. Among the total number of respondents, 28 students, comprising 93.33% of the sample, were 12 years old, while the remaining 2 students, making up 6.67% of the sample, were 13 years old. In terms of gender distribution, 17 participants (56.67%) were male, while 13 participants (43.33%) were female. These participants were selected based on their performance in the Oral Reading Assessment, which was conducted at the beginning of the school year as part of the school's utilization of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI) developed by the Department of Education. The struggling readers were the students who performed below a certain proficiency threshold on the assessment and since they were facing challenges and difficulties in developing their reading skills at the expected level for their age and grade level, they needed additional support and intervention to improve their reading abilities.

IV. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In this study, the researcher used a purposive sampling to obtain the sample. According to Crossman [10], purposive sampling involves selecting participants based on specific shared characteristics or sets of characteristics, rather than on random selection. This process of selecting this sample was done by taking subject that was not based on the area or level but were chosen based on the specific purpose. Since the goal of this research was to improve the reading fluency of struggling readers with use of Repeated Reading Strategy, the sample that represented the population of the struggling readers was obtained using the result of the Individual Oral Reading Assessment conducted by the researcher using the PHIL IRI Manual 2018.

The 30 respondents were chosen purposively by the researcher since they were all identified as struggling readers of Pres. Jose P. Laurel National High School in the Division of Tanauan City for the School Year 2022-2023. They were the learners whose Word Recognition Scores fall under the Frustration Level. By using purposive sampling, the researcher ensured that the participants chosen for the study had the specific characteristics necessary to achieve the research objectives. In this case, the selected participants represented the population of struggling readers and were the focus of the intervention utilizing the Repeated Reading Strategy.

V. RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Since the school where the respondents belonged was being monitored by the Division in its conduct of the Learning Recovery Continuity Plan focusing on reading, the researcher was able to identify if the students had benefited from the Repeated Reading Strategy that was utilized as part of the Reading Intervention Activity of the school.

To obtain data from this research, the researcher utilized Assessment Tools for the Pre- Test and Post- Test, 10 Phil IRI Reading Passages, Progress Monitoring Chart and Prosody Scoring Guide which were vital in the conduct of Repeated Reading Strategy.

To measure the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy in developing the reading fluency of struggling readers in Grade 7, the researcher utilized the pre- and post-assessment tools designed specifically for this study. These assessment tools measured the participants' reading fluency in terms of accuracy, rate, and prosody both before and after the intervention utilizing the Repeated Reading Strategy.

The pre-test assessment tool consisted of 193 words, while the post-test assessment tool consisted of 196 words. Both assessments were appropriate for Grade 7 learners as they were expected to read text up to 204 words per minute.

The mentioned assessment tools were carefully designed by the researcher to ensure that they accurately measured the participants' reading fluency and were aligned with the objectives of the study. The pre- and post-assessment tools enabled the researcher to measure the participants' progress and the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy in improving their reading fluency.

To ensure that there will be a systematic process of intervention to be conducted to the identified struggling readers, a lesson exemplar was designed by the researcher indicating how the one-on-one session with the learner will take place. This lesson exemplar was considered a valuable instrument in a repeated reading strategy session with each learner that serves as a model or guide that demonstrates the desired reading behaviors, techniques, and strategies that the learners should aim to develop during the session.

For the conduct of intervention, each session involved the use of Graded Reading Passages from the PHIL IRI Manual 2018. The PHIL IRI (Philippine Informal Reading Inventory) is a widely used reading assessment tool in the Philippines, which provides a comprehensive analysis of students' reading abilities, including their reading levels, strengths, and weaknesses.

The Graded Reading Passages were used during the intervention sessions with the identified struggling readers in Grade 7. These passages were carefully selected based on the participants' reading levels, ensuring that they were appropriate for the participants' reading abilities.

During the intervention sessions, the participants were asked to read the Graded Reading Passages aloud repeatedly, using the Repeated Reading Strategy. The Repeated Reading Strategy involves reading the same text multiple times, with the goal of improving reading fluency with accuracy, appropriate rate and prosody.

By employing the Graded Reading Passages during the intervention sessions, the researcher was able to provide the participants with appropriate reading materials that were aligned with their reading levels. Moreover, the use of the Repeated Reading Strategy allowed the participants to practice reading the same text multiple times, which was believed to be an effective way to enhance their reading fluency.

To monitor the progress of each struggling reader during the intervention sessions, the researcher provided Learners' Progress Charts. These charts served as a tool in tracking down the reader's performance after each session. The progress chart had columns for the day, the reading passage set, total errors or miscues, their prosody score and their rate reflecting the number of words they had read per minute.

The mentioned progress chart helped the researcher to identify if the reader was making progress in terms of accuracy, rate, and prosody, which are the components of reading fluency. It also served as a basis for the researcher to adjust the instructional approach and tailor-fit it to the reader's needs.

Moreover, these progress charts motivated the learners as they witnessed their progress throughout the sessions. By seeing the improvement they had made, they were encouraged to put in more effort and strive harder to achieve better results.

After each reading session, the Prosody Scoring Guide, a tool developed to evaluate a reader's prosodic reading skills, was used to assess the learners' ability to incorporate proper expression, volume, phrasing, and smoothness in their reading.

The researcher used the stated Prosody Scoring Rubric to determine if the struggling readers were making progress in terms of their prosodic reading skills. By incorporating repeated reading with the teacher, the learners were expected to improve their prosody and fluency in reading. The Prosody Scoring Rubric then helped the researcher to quantify the improvements made by the learners and identify specific areas that needed further development.

In this way, the Prosody Scoring Rubric was a valuable tool in assessing the effectiveness of the repeated reading strategy in enhancing the reading fluency of struggling readers. By providing immediate feedback and corrective measures, the Prosody Scoring Rubric helped the learners to improve their prosodic reading skills more effectively.

Furthermore, to ensure effective error correction and monitoring of oral reading miscues, a separate reading passage was used by the reading teacher. This passage was used to track the learner's progress and identify areas where they may be struggling. By conducting error correction during the initial oral reading activity, the reading teacher was able to easily point out to the learner the mistakes they had made and provided immediate feedback on how to correct them. This approach helped the struggling readers to focus on specific

areas of improvement and work towards enhancing their reading fluency.

Overall, the utilization of the above- mentioned instruments provided a standardized and reliable measure of the participants' reading fluency development throughout the intervention period. These then enabled the researcher to determine the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy as a tool for enhancing the reading fluency of struggling readers in Grade 7.

To satisfy the requirement of this research, the weighted mean and standard deviation were used to measure the scores of the respondents during the conduct of Pre-and Post-Individual Oral Reading Assessment.

In addition, the two-tailed p- value was used to compare the means of the data obtained from the respondents and to measure if there was a significant difference between the result of the Pre- Test and Post- Test provided to the research respondents.

To obtain the Accuracy Level of the Respondents, the researcher used the scale from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual 2018 as shown in the table below:

Table 1: Phil IRI Reading Profile as to Accuracy

Reading Fluency Level	Word Recognition Score
Independent	97-100%
Instructional	90-96%
Frustration	89% and below

Regarding the rate or word count per minute, the following scale was then applied:

Table 2: Phil IRI Reading Profile as to Rate

Reading Fluency Level	Rate or Word Count Per Minute
Independent	150-204 WCPM
Instructional	81-150 WCPM
Frustration	80 WCPM AND BELOW

Lastly, to check the prosodic level of the respondents, the scale below was then used:

Table 3: Phil IRI Reading Profile as to Prosody

Reading Fluency Level	Prosody
Independent	9-12
Instructional	5-8
Frustration	1-4

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents an in-depth analysis and interpretation of the data collected during the research process. The findings are presented in tabular form followed by detailed explanations of the results. Through a thorough examination of the data, this chapter will provide insights that will serve as the basis for drawing conclusions and making recommendations based on the research objectives.

Table 4: Performance in Reading Fluency before Repeated Reading Strategy

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Accuracy	87.96	4.29	Frustration
Rate	79.07	24.35	Frustration
Prosody	4.80	1.65	Instructional

Table 4 provides information about the performance in reading fluency of Grade 7 struggling readers in their pre-assessment before the use of Repeated Reading Strategy, in terms of three variables: Accuracy, Rate, and Prosody.

The mean and standard deviation for each variable are provided, along with an interpretation of their performance level. Based on the data, the mean score for accuracy is 87.96, with a standard deviation of 4.29. This places their performance level in the “frustration” range, indicating that they are having difficulty with accurate reading.

The mean score for rate is 79.07, with a standard deviation of 24.35. This also places their performance level in the “frustration” range, indicating that they are having difficulty with reading at an appropriate speed.

Finally, the mean score for prosody is 4.80, with a standard deviation of 1.65. This places their performance level in the “Instructional” range, indicating that they are showing some proficiency in reading with appropriate expression and phrasing, but could still benefit from further instruction and practice.

The mean scores for Accuracy and Rate indicate that the students were performing below the expected level for their current grade. This further suggests that they were struggling with reading fluency and were likely having trouble comprehending and retaining information from the texts they were reading.

The mean score for Prosody, on the other hand, indicates that the students had some level of proficiency in reading with appropriate expression, volume, phrasing and smoothness. However, the fact that their mean score was at the lower end of the instructional range suggests that they could still benefit from further instruction and support in this area.

Overall, Table 4 clearly indicates that the poor scores in accuracy, rate, and prosody of the students before the intervention reflect the challenges faced by struggling readers in various aspects of reading fluency. These challenges can

hinder their overall reading comprehension and impact their academic progress. Thus, this highlights the need for intervention to improve the reading fluency skills of Grade 7 struggling readers before they can progress effectively in their studies. Based on the study by Rasinski and Padak [9], they found out that the Repeated Reading Strategy has improved both accuracy and rate in struggling readers. The study also found that the said strategy had improved students' comprehension and motivation to read. With this, the researcher believes that the use of Repeated Reading Strategy may be a useful intervention to improve the readers' accuracy and rate in reading, while also further developing their prosody skills.

Table 5: Performance in Reading Fluency after Repeated Reading Strategy

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Accuracy	93.87	3.85	Instructional
Rate	89.00	22.39	Instructional
Prosody	7.37	2.22	Instructional

Table 5 shows the performance of struggling readers in Grade 7 in their post-assessment after the use of Repeated Reading Strategy, specifically in terms of the three variables: Accuracy, Rate, and Prosody.

To establish conclusions if there is an improvement in the fluency level of the respondents after the conduct of the reading intervention, the mean and standard deviation are provided with corresponding interpretation.

Based on the gathered data, the mean score for accuracy is 93.87, with a standard deviation of 3.85. This then places the performance level of the respondents in the “instructional” range, indicating that they have improved their ability to read accurately. This implies that the repeated reading practice and learners' exposure to reading texts led to the students' attainment of progress in reading texts or passages with accuracy. Furthermore, this data indicates that the word recognition level of the respondents has increased since most of them were able to read the post- assessment instrument with few errors or oral miscues. It can be inferred that Repeated Reading Strategy greatly develops readers' accuracy level. This is supported by the study conducted by Chard, Vaughn, and Tyler [10] wherein they had found out that repeated reading, combined with instruction in phonics and word recognition, improved struggling readers' accuracy in reading. The study further revealed that students who received repeated reading instruction made significant gains in reading accuracy compared to students who did not receive the intervention.

Furthermore, table 5 also reveals the progress attained by the struggling readers in terms of rate. The mean score for rate is 89.00, with a standard deviation of 22.39. This also places their performance level in the “Instructional” range, indicating that they have improved their reading speed after the use of the Repeated Reading Strategy. This only suggests that this strategy is an evidence- based strategy considered to be an

effective way to improve students' reading rate. The strategy used, involving the reading of a text for several times, has allowed the learner to achieve the certain level of fluency since the repeated reading practice helped them become more familiar with the words and structures of the text which led them to have an increased reading speed.

This result is also evident with the study conducted by Therrien and Kubina [11] in which they found out that repeated reading, combined with a self-monitoring strategy, improved struggling readers' reading rate. Their study then revealed that students who received repeated reading instruction made significant improvements in reading rate compared to students who were not involved in the reading practice.

Finally, in terms of knowing how the Repeated Reading Strategy will help the readers' manner of reading English texts, the data reveals that the mean score for Prosody is 7.37, with a standard deviation of 2.22 after the conduct of the reading intervention. This places the performance level of the respondents in the "Instructional" range, indicating that they have improved their ability to read with appropriate expression, volume, phrasing and smoothness. The data only

proves that repeated reading is an effective strategy to develop the overall reading ability of the learners for as readers become more familiar with the text through repeated readings, they are better able to focus on these aspects of oral reading and adjust their delivery accordingly.

Supporting these findings is a study conducted by Rasinski and colleague [9] wherein they revealed that repeated reading was found to significantly improve the prosody of struggling readers. Students who participated in repeated reading practice showed significant gains in expression, phrasing, and overall fluency. These improvements in prosody were also found to transfer to new texts, indicating that the benefits of repeated reading were not limited to the specific texts used in the practice sessions.

Overall, the data in Table 6 suggests that the use of Repeated Reading Strategy has been effective and beneficial in improving the Reading Fluency performance of grade 7 struggling readers, particularly in terms of Accuracy, Rate, and Prosody. The mean scores for all three variables have improved and are now in the instructional range, suggesting that the students have made significant progress in their reading abilities.

Table 6: Test of Difference between the Performances of the Grade 7 Struggling Readers in the Pre-Assessment and Post-Assessment before and after the use of Repeated Reading Strategy

Variables	Pre-assessment		Post-assessment		T	DF	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Accuracy	87.96	4.29	93.87	3.85	11.783	29	.002	Significant
Rate	79.07	24.3	89.00	22.39	4.609	29	.001	Significant
Prosody	4.80	1.65	7.37	2.22	11.000	29	.001	Significant

Table 7 presents the results of a test of difference that was conducted to determine if there was a significant difference between the performance of struggling readers in grade 7 in their pre-assessment and post-assessment before and after the use of Repeated Reading Strategy in terms of the three variables: Accuracy, Rate, and Prosody.

The table also includes the mean and standard deviation (SD) for each variable in both the pre-assessment and post-assessment conditions, as well as the t-value, degrees of freedom (df), and the significance level (p-value) for a two-tailed test.

Based on the results, there is a significant difference between the mean scores of the three variables namely: Accuracy, Rate and Prosody in the pre- and post-assessments.

In terms of accuracy, there was a significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment scores. The mean score increased from 87.96 in the pre-assessment to 93.87 in the post-assessment, indicating an improvement. The standard deviation for both assessments remained relatively stable. The t-value was 11.783 with 29 degrees of freedom, and the p-value (Sig.) was .002. This indicates that the increase in accuracy was statistically significant, suggesting that the Repeated Reading Strategy had a positive impact on improving the accuracy of Grade 7 struggling readers.

The large t-value of 11.783 further supports the significance of the result, indicating a substantial difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment scores. This suggests that the improvement in accuracy is not merely due to chance or random fluctuations in performance.

For the Rate, the mean score increased from 79.07 in the pre-assessment to 89.00 in the post-assessment, with a slight decrease in the standard deviation. The t-value is 7.520, with 29 degrees of freedom, and the p-value (Sig.) is .001, which is less than .05. This suggests that there is a significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment performance level of the identified struggling readers in terms of Rate. This further suggests that the use of Repeated Reading Strategy had a significant positive effect on the reading rate of the struggling readers in grade 7.

One possible reason for the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the learners in the use of Repeated Reading Strategy in terms of Rate could be the positive impact of repeated exposure to reading passages. According to a study by Rasinski and Padak[9], repeated reading can lead to improved reading fluency because it increases the learners' familiarity with the text, allowing them to read more quickly and accurately over time. Additionally, the repetitive nature of the Repeated Reading Strategy enables learners to develop automaticity in word recognition, allowing them to read more quickly and accurately.

Furthermore, in terms of Prosody, the mean score increased from 4.80 in the pre-assessment to 7.37 in the post-assessment, with an increase in the standard deviation. The t-value is 7.274, with 29 degrees of freedom, and the p-value (Sig.) is .001, which is also less than .05. The result then suggests that there is a significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment performance level of the respondents as far as prosody is concerned. This only implies that the use of Repeated Reading Strategy had a significant impact on the struggling readers' ability to read the text with appropriate expression, volume, phrasing and smoothness.

The significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of learners in the use of the Repeated Reading Strategy in terms of prosody can be attributed to the intervention's emphasis on accuracy, fluency, and expression. The Repeated Reading Strategy allowed learners to repeatedly read passages until they became more familiar with the text, resulting in increased reading speed, smoother phrasing, and better expression.

In the study conducted by Fuchs, Fuchs, Hosp, and Jenkins [12] yielded similar findings, indicating that the Repeated Reading Strategy positively impacted students' prosody. The strategy improved students' attention to phrasing and expression, resulting in more natural and fluent reading. Additionally, the study highlighted that repeated reading helped students develop self-monitoring skills, enabling them to identify errors in their prosody and ultimately enhancing their accuracy and fluency in reading.

Overall, the data in Table 7 suggests that the implementation of the Repeated Reading Strategy has resulted in a noteworthy enhancement in the reading fluency of struggling readers in grade 7. The three variables of accuracy,

rate, and prosody all demonstrated significant improvements after the intervention. The increase in the mean scores suggests that students were able to read with greater precision and make fewer errors when reading passages. Struggling readers were able to develop a better sense of rhythm, phrasing, and intonation, which are important aspects of prosody, after the conduct of repeated readings. Additionally, repeated reading has increased the students' automaticity, which led to a smoother and more efficient reading process, resulting in improved reading speed. Thus, the findings strongly supported the effectiveness of the Repeated Reading Strategy as an intervention to develop reading fluency among struggling readers in grade 7 since students have become more precise, faster, and more expressive readers after the utilization of the reading intervention. The acquisition of these skills is believed crucial for struggling readers to enhance their overall reading comprehension and eventually become more fluent and efficient readers of English texts.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the data and statistical analysis, the results of the study reject the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the performances in reading fluency of the struggling readers in the pre-assessment and post-assessment before and after the use of the Repeated Reading Strategy in terms of accuracy, rate, and prosody. The findings demonstrate a clear and substantial improvement in the three variables of reading fluency after implementing the Repeated Reading Strategy. The significant increases in accuracy, rate, and prosody indicate that the intervention had a positive impact on the students' reading fluency skills. These results provide strong evidence that the Repeated Reading Strategy effectively enhances the reading fluency of struggling readers.

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: (1) Since the study revealed that the use of Repeated Reading Strategy is effective in enhancing the reading fluency of the struggling students in Grade 7, English teachers should consider incorporating this strategy into their reading instruction to provide students with ample opportunities for repeated practice, which can lead to an improved accuracy, rate, and prosody; (2) teachers of other areas of discipline may also use this technique in their subject intervention to enhance the fluency of their students in reading subject-related texts for this may lead to the learners' better engagement in their subject matter. By prioritizing reading fluency across all subject areas, students can develop strong reading skills that can benefit them academically and in their future careers; and (3) future researchers may use this as a reference for their study. They may conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term effects of the Repeated Reading Strategy on reading fluency and other reading-related outcomes. Tracking students' progress over an extended period will provide valuable insights into the sustainability and transferability of fluency gains.

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